

Participant Information Leaflet- Adolescent participant

Participant ID.....

Title of Research: Evaluation of High Dose Rifampicin and Dialkylcarbamoyl chloride (DACC)-coated dressings to improve outcomes in *Mycobacterium ulcerans* disease

Name(s) and affiliation(s) of researcher(s) of applicant(s):

This study is being conducted by Prof Richard O. Phillips of Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology and Kumasi Centre for Collaborative Research in Tropical Medicine (KCCR)/ KNUST, Dr. Michael Marks of London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM) and other researchers in Ghana and Europe.

Purpose(s) of research: The aim of the study is to determine the ability of high-dose Rifampicin and DACC dressing (HR-DACC) to improve the time to clearance of viable mycobacterium from Buruli ulcer wounds compared to a regimen using standard dose Rifampicin and DACC dressings (SR-DACC).

Background information

The wound or the swelling you have is caused by an organism called *Mycobacterium ulcerans*. There are several approaches for managing this condition. One is the availability of antibiotics (usually standard rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin) that can be used to treat the disease once it is confirmed as Buruli ulcer. These drugs kill the organism that is causing the disease. Rifampicin is the main drug used for treatment. Scientist have found out that a higher dose of the drug is safe and can help improve healing outcome and may shorten the period/ duration for taking the drugs.

Those with wounds also go through wound dressing procedures at the hospitals and the various health centers in the communities. Some materials used include Vaseline gauze and bandages. However, we have observed that some people heal faster than others even with the antibiotic treatment. Some still have living organisms in their wounds many weeks after the antibiotic treatment. There is a new dressing material called DACC which Scientists believe permanently binds bacteria (organisms) on the wound surface leading to their removal when the dressings are changed. This is a good way to prevent infection without the use of more drugs.

We want to test the high dose Rifampicin to see how it can shorten the healing time. We also want to test this new material (DACC) to see if it helps to prevent infection and improve the time of healing in Buruli ulcer wounds.

By doing so we will see if this can help kill the bacteria more quickly and speed up wound healing. We will also collect data to help us see the cost of these different treatments and the impact that Buruli ulcer and its treatment have on you/your family's income or ability to work or study. Both groups will receive the same care and we will monitor everyone. We will use computer to do this so we don't know who will take the high dose Rifampicin or standard dose Rifampicin treatment.

Nature of Research

Procedure of the research, what shall be required of each participant and approximate total number of participants that would be involved in the research:

Role of investigators

Before we let you take part in the study, we will explain to you further and give you time to understand and ask questions. We will let you sign and officially become part of the study. We will do a short physical examination and ask you questions about your Buruli ulcer (swelling or wound) and your current life. We will examine the Buruli ulcer, measure and take photo of the wound. We will give you antibiotics (either standard or high dose rifampicin in combination with Clarithromycin) once we confirm you have Buruli ulcer depending on the group you fall in. All patients will receive the new DACC dressing materials. We will monitor your healing progress and ask you questions anytime we see you to ensure your safety. We will take fine needle aspirates or swabs from the swelling or wound.

Role of participants

You will be given antibiotics either a combination of rifampicin 20mg/kg and clarithromycin 15mg/kg for 4 weeks or rifampicin 10mg/kg and clarithromycin 15mg/kg for 8 weeks and a new treatment dressing (DACC) to put on your sores and they will be changed every other day for 8 weeks.

As part of participants' responsibility to the study, you will be invited to arrive at the center where the study is performed during an already scheduled time for a hospital visit. When you start treatment, you will be required to come for reviews at weeks 2, 4, 6, 8 and monthly until the 12th month when your sore heals completely and we are sure of no recurrence.

However, in this period of COVID-19 pandemic, you may be scheduled for monthly visits only once your lesion heals even during the period of taking antibiotics. You will be given the drugs to cover the period before the next review and you will be monitored by the health volunteer from your community/ village.

Anytime you notice anything unusual once you start taking the antibiotics and the dressing materials, report to the doctors that come to see you. You can also call the numbers provided on this form in case you require any assistance or clarification.

Samples to be taken and their uses

To know if the swelling or wound you have is Buruli ulcer, we will take fluid with needle called fine needle aspirate from the swelling and/ or cotton swab sample from the wound, to know if the organism causing the Buruli ulcer is alive or not and to also find out if there are other organisms present in the wound that can cause secondary infections. We will take these samples at weeks 0,2,4,6,8 and at week 12 and 16 if your wound does not heal.

These samples will be transported and examined in the laboratory at KCCR in Kumasi to determine if the disease is Buruli ulcer. All biological samples obtained from you for this study will be analysed within the lifetime of the project which is 5 years. Permission will be sought from the ethics committee of the Ghana Health Service and Food and Drugs Authority (FDA) should there be any unanticipated delay.

Number of participants

A total of approximately 112 participants will be recruited into the study; half will use the high dose rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin 15mg/kg daily and the other half will use the standard dose rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin 15mg/kg daily. All patients

will receive DACC material for their wound dressing.

Risk(s):

There are no substantial risks from the samples that would be taken. Sample collection for the study is in line with standard diagnostic procedures carried out as part of routine patient care. Samples for diagnosis will be collected either via a swab or fine needle aspiration. Fine needle aspirates may cause minor pain. All procedures will be conducted by trained personnel. The new dressing may cause itch from the adhesive; when this occurs, report to the doctor immediately.

Taking this new drug (Rifampicin), you may experience some reactions which may include dizziness, fever, headache, itching, and skin rash but not limited. You are encouraged to talk to your doctor anytime you have an unusual feeling after taking this drug.

We will minimize this risk by getting a qualified person to take the blood under sterile conditions. Any additional medical or nursing care will be delivered free of charge as is done in the routine care of all other patients with Buruli ulcer.

Benefit(s):

There are no direct benefits to you, but the information we collect will be helpful for future Buruli ulcer patients, as we learn more about how your body adjust to the presence of Buruli ulcer germs in your body. Standard diagnostic tests done at the KCCR to confirm if the disease is Buruli ulcer or not will be done free of charge. The laboratory tests done free of charge will also help your doctor to manage you better.

Dissemination

Once the study results become available, they will be explained to the participants in lay terms and also to the community leaders. In addition, the results will be presented to the hospital staff at the study site. The results will be presented to the National Buruli Ulcer Control Programme at the National Steering committee meeting and to the local communities. Results will be provided to the Ethics Committee; the Regulatory bodies on request. Results may be published in open access peer reviewed journals and progress of study presented at the annual WHO meeting on Buruli ulcer.

Confidentiality:

We will keep confidential any information related to this study and all data and records generated in the course of conducting the study, and will not use the information, data, or records for any purpose other than those specified in this study protocol.

All information collected in this study will be given code numbers. No name will be recorded. Data collected cannot be linked to you in anyway. No name or identifier will be used in any publication or reports from this study.

All the study information will be kept securely either in the archive at the KCCR or on password protected computer for 10 years after which they will be discarded. Only the investigators will have full access to your data. To ensure your safety and protocol adherence, all data records and other trial related documents will be made available to the Ghana FDA or the trial sponsor (LSHTM) during Good Clinical Practice (GCP) inspections.

Voluntariness:

Taking part in this study should be out of your own free will. You are not under any obligation to participate; it is entirely voluntary. Take your time to think about it and feel free to discuss

with family members, elders and others. You will have 48 hours to consider whether you are willing to participate or not. Even after agreeing to participate you have the right to withdraw later, without the need to explain why you are withdrawing. If you withdraw we will not keep any further information about you.

Alternatives to participation:

If you choose not to participate, it will be of no consequence to you, and you will not be approached again. You will receive standard medical treatment which consists of at least 8 weeks of antibiotics and gauze dressings.

Withdrawal from the research:

You may choose to withdraw from the research at any time without having to explain yourself. You may also choose not to answer any question you find uncomfortable or private. New information that is relevant to you as a study participant will be made known to you appropriately and you may choose to withdraw from the study or continue with it based on the information given to you.

Consequences of Withdrawal:

Don't feel obliged to participate: this decision is yours. Even after you decided to participate you may still reconsider and decide to withdraw even if you signed to participate earlier. You are not obliged to explain why you changed your mind: you alone may decide to continue in the study or not. If you withdraw, this will not affect the way you will be treated. Also, even if you want to continue, the doctor may decide that it is in your best interest to withdraw from the study. He or she will explain why this should happen. If you don't feel like participating in the study, there will be no adverse consequence and no loss of benefit or care.

Costs/Compensation:

The study will take up some of your time. As a compensation for your participation, you will be given small supplies of food worth 30GhC (5.5 euros) and vitamin supplements. Also, any costs related to this study (including transport – about GHs 10), will be reimbursed based on your distance from the clinic. Any other cost you incur in transportation to the clinic due to COVID-19 will be reimbursed. Standard PCR diagnostic tests done at the laboratory to confirm if the disease is Buruli ulcer or not will be paid for by this research study. This provision will also cover those that do not agree to participate. Any ill effect of the treatment requiring additional medical or nursing care will be delivered free of charge.

Contacts:

If you have any question concerning this study, please do not hesitate to contact Dr Yaw Ampem Amoako of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital on 0244858075.

If you have any concern about the conduct of this study, your welfare or your rights as a research participant, you may contact:

The Chairman

Committee on Human Research and Publications Ethics

KNUST - Kumasi

Tel: +233 3220 63248 / +233 20 545 3785

You may also contact the administrator of Ghana health service Ethics Review Committee, Nana Abena Apatu on 050 353 9896 in case you have any concern.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION FOR COVID-19

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a communicable respiratory disease caused by a new strain of coronavirus that causes illness in humans.

Know how it spreads

- There is currently no vaccine to prevent coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).
- **The best way to prevent illness is to avoid being exposed to this virus.**
- The virus is thought to spread mainly from person-to-person.
 - Between people who are in close contact with one another (within about 6 feet).
 - Through respiratory droplets produced when an infected person coughs, sneezes or talks.
 - These droplets can land in the mouths or noses of people who are nearby or possibly be inhaled into the lungs.
 - Some recent studies have suggested that COVID-19 may be spread by people who are not showing symptoms.

Symptoms

People with COVID-19 have had a wide range of symptoms reported – ranging from mild symptoms to severe illness.

Symptoms may appear **2-14 days after exposure to the virus**. People with these symptoms **may** have COVID-19:

- Fever or chills
- New loss of taste or smell
- Cough
- Shortness of breath or difficulty breathing
- Fatigue
- Muscle or body aches
- Headache
- Sore throat
- Congestion or runny nose
- Nausea or vomiting
- Diarrhea

Best Health Practices

There is currently no vaccine or treatment for COVID-19

Infection can be prevented by observing personal hygiene practices:

Hand Washing

Wash your hands often

- Wash your hands often with soap and water for at least 20 seconds especially after you have been in a public place, or after blowing your nose, coughing, or sneezing.
- If soap and water are not readily available, **use a hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol**. Cover all surfaces of your hands and rub them together until they feel dry.
- **Avoid touching your eyes, nose, and mouth** with unwashed hands.

Avoid close contact

- **Avoid close contact with people who are sick, even inside your home.** If possible, maintain 6 feet between the person who is sick and other household members.
- **Put distance between yourself and other people outside of your home.**
 - Remember that some people without symptoms may be able to spread virus.
 - Stay at least 6 feet (about 2 arms' length) from other people.
 - Do not gather in groups.
 - Stay out of crowded places and avoid mass gatherings.
 - Keeping distance from others is especially important for people who are at higher risk of getting very sick.

Cover your mouth and nose with a cloth face cover when around others

- You could spread COVID-19 to others even if you do not feel sick.
- Everyone should wear a cloth face cover when they have to go out in public, for example to the grocery store or to pick up other necessities.
 - Cloth face coverings should not be placed on young children under age 2, anyone who has trouble breathing, or is unconscious, incapacitated or otherwise unable to remove the mask without assistance.
- The cloth face cover is meant to protect other people in case you are infected.
- Do NOT use a facemask meant for a healthcare worker.
- Continue to keep about 6 feet between yourself and others. The cloth face cover is not a substitute for social distancing.

Cover coughs and sneezes

- **If you are in a private setting and do not have on your cloth face covering, remember to always cover your mouth and nose** with a tissue when you cough or sneeze or use the inside of your elbow.
- **Throw used tissues** in the trash.
- Immediately **wash your hands** with soap and water for at least 20 seconds. If soap and water are not readily available, clean your hands with a hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol.

Clean and disinfect

- **Clean AND disinfect frequently touched surfaces daily.** This includes tables, doorknobs, light switches, countertops, handles, desks, phones, keyboards, toilets, faucets, and sinks.
- **If surfaces are dirty, clean them.** Use detergent or soap and water prior to disinfection.
- **Then, use a household disinfectant.**

Monitor Your Health

- **Be alert for symptoms.** Watch for fever, cough, shortness of breath, or other symptoms of **COVID-19**.

Health Facility

If you have more severe symptoms go to a medical facility and immediately notify the first person you encounter that you are worried that you have a respiratory infection.

For our Study,

- We will ask that you will always wear a face mask before coming to the clinic. If you do not have one, we will provide you with one which you will wear throughout the procedures.
- Kindly comply with us when we ask that you wash your hands with soap under running water/alcohol-based sanitizers.
- In the examination room, we will ensure that not more than two health workers/ researchers attend to you. if they are more than that, kindly draw their attention to it.
- We will introduce a new sitting arrangement at the waiting are; kindly comply with this anytime you come for review to ensure proper social distancing protocols.

CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF RESEARCH: EVALUATION OF HIGH DOSE RIFAMPICIN AND DIALKYL CARBAMOYL CHLORIDE (DACC)-COATED DRESSINGS TO IMPROVE OUTCOMES IN MYCOBACTERIUM ULCERANS DISEASE

PARTICIPANTS' STATEMENT

Child/young person (or if unable to, parent on their behalf) to complete	Please circle all you agree with:	
Have you read (or had read to you) information about this project?	Yes	No
Has somebody else explained this project to you?	Yes	No
Do you understand what this project is about?	Yes	No
Have you had any questions answered in a way you understand?	Yes	No
Do you understand that it is ok to stop taking part at any time?	Yes	No
Are you happy to take part?	Yes	No

I agree to be part of this research.

Name of Participant.....

Participants' SignatureOR Thumb Print.....

Date:.....

INTERPRETERS' STATEMENT

I interpreted the purpose and contents of the Participants' Information Sheet to the afore named participant to the best of my ability in the (English / Twi) language to his proper understanding.

All questions, appropriate clarifications sort by the participant and answers were also duly interpreted to his/her satisfaction.

Name of Interpreter.....

Signature of Interpreter..... OR Thumb Print

Date:.....

Contact Details

STATEMENT OF WITNESS

I was present when the purpose and contents of the Participant Information Sheet was read and explained satisfactorily to the participant in the language he/she understood (English / Twi)

I confirm that he/she was given the opportunity to ask questions/seek clarifications and same were duly answered to his/her satisfaction before voluntarily agreeing to be part of the research.

Name:.....

Signature.....

Date:.....

INVESTIGATOR STATEMENT AND SIGNATURE

Brief statement or declaration that investigator has given enough information to participants to make informed decisions.

I certify that the participant has been given ample time to read and learn about the study. All questions and clarifications raised by the participant have been addressed.

Researcher's name.....

Signature

Date.....

Participant Information Leaflet- Parent/ Guardians of child participants

Participant ID.....

Title of Research: Evaluation of High Dose Rifampicin and Dialkylcarbamoyl chloride (DACC)-coated dressings to improve outcomes in *Mycobacterium ulcerans* disease

Name(s) and affiliation(s) of researcher(s) of applicant(s):

This study is being conducted by Prof Richard O. Phillips of Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology and Kumasi Centre for Collaborative Research in Tropical Medicine (KCCR)/ KNUST, Dr. Michael Marks of London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM) and other researchers in Ghana and Europe.

Purpose(s) of research: The aim of the study is to determine the ability of high-dose Rifampicin and DACC dressing (HR-DACC) to improve the time to clearance of viable mycobacterium from Buruli ulcer wounds compared to a regimen using standard dose Rifampicin and DACC dressings (SR-DACC).

Background information

The wound or the swelling your child has is caused by an organism called *Mycobacterium ulcerans*. There are several approaches for managing this condition. One is the availability of antibiotics (usually standard rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin) that can be used to treat the disease once it is confirmed as Buruli ulcer. These drugs kill the organism that is causing the disease. Rifampicin is the main drug used for treatment. Scientist have found out that a higher dose of the drug is safe and can help improve healing outcome and may shorten the period/ duration for taking the drugs.

Those with wounds also go through wound dressing procedures at the hospitals and the various health centers in the communities. Some materials used include Vaseline gauze and bandages. However, we have observed that some people heal faster than others even with the antibiotic treatment. Some still have living organisms in their wounds many weeks after the antibiotic treatment. There is a new dressing material called DACC which Scientists believe permanently binds bacteria (organisms) on the wound surface leading to their removal when the dressings are changed. This is a good way to prevent infection without the use of more drugs.

We want to test the high dose Rifampicin to see how it can shorten the healing time. We also want to test this new material (DACC) to see if it helps to prevent infection and improve the time of healing in Buruli ulcer wounds.

By doing so we will see if this can help kill the bacteria more quickly and speed up wound healing. We will also collect data to help us see the cost of these different treatments and the impact that Buruli ulcer and its treatment have on you/your family's income or ability to work or study. Both groups will receive the same care and we will monitor everyone. We will use computer to do this so we don't know who will take the high dose Rifampicin or standard dose Rifampicin treatment.

Nature of Research

Procedure of the research, what shall be required of each participant and approximate total number of participants that would be involved in the research:

Role of investigators

Before we let your child take part in the study, we will explain to you further and give you time to understand and ask questions. We will let you sign and your child officially become part of the study. We will do a short physical examination and ask you questions about your Buruli ulcer (swelling or wound) and your current life. We will examine the Buruli ulcer, measure and take photo of the wound. We will give your child antibiotics (either standard or high dose rifampicin in combination with Clarithromycin) once we confirm you have Buruli ulcer depending on the group you fall in. All patients will receive the new DACC dressing materials. We will monitor your child's healing progress and ask them and you questions anytime we see them to ensure your safety. We will take fine needle aspirates or swabs from the swelling or wound.

Role of participants

Your child will be given antibiotics either a combination of rifampicin 20mg/kg and clarithromycin 15mg/kg for 4 weeks or rifampicin 10mg/kg and clarithromycin 15mg/kg for 8 weeks and a new treatment dressing (DACC) to put on your child's sores and they will be changed every other day for 8 weeks.

As part of participants' responsibility to the study, your child will be invited to arrive at the center where the study is performed during an already scheduled time for a hospital visit. When your child starts treatment, you will be required to come for reviews at weeks 2, 4, 6, 8 and monthly until the 12th month when your sore heals completely and we are sure of no recurrence.

However, in this period of COVID-19 pandemic, your child may be scheduled for monthly visits only once your lesion heals even during the period of taking antibiotics. Your child will be given the drugs to cover the period before the next review and you will be monitored by the health volunteer from your community/ village.

Anytime you notice anything unusual once your child starts taking the antibiotics and the dressing materials, report to the doctors that come to see you. You can also call the numbers provided on this form in case you require any assistance or clarification.

Samples to be taken and their uses

To know if the swelling or wound your child has is Buruli ulcer, we will take fluid with needle called fine needle aspirate from the swelling and/ or cotton swab sample from the wound, to know if the organism causing the Buruli ulcer is alive or not and to also find out if there are other organisms present in the wound that can cause secondary infections. We will take these samples at weeks 0,2,4,6,8 and at week 12 and 16 if your wound does not heal.

These samples will be transported and examined in the laboratory at KCCR in Kumasi to determine if the disease is Buruli ulcer. All biological samples obtained from your child for this study will be analysed within the lifetime of the project which is 5 years. Permission will be sought from the ethics committee of the Ghana Health Service and Food and Drugs Authority (FDA) should there be any unanticipated delay.

Number of participants

A total of approximately 112 participants will be recruited into the study; half will use the high dose rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin 15mg/kg daily and the other half will use

the standard dose rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin 15mg/kg daily. All patients will receive DACC material for their wound dressing.

Risk(s):

There are no substantial risks from the samples that would be taken. Sample collection for the study is in line with standard diagnostic procedures carried out as part of routine patient care. Samples for diagnosis will be collected either via a swab or fine needle aspiration. Fine needle aspirates may cause minor pain. All procedures will be conducted by trained personnel. The new dressing may cause itch from the adhesive; when this occurs, report to the doctor immediately.

Taking this new drug (Rifampicin), your child may experience some reactions which may include dizziness, fever, headache, itching, and skin rash but not limited. You are encouraged to talk to your doctor anytime you have an unusual feeling after taking this drug.

We will minimize this risk by getting a qualified person to perform all procedures. Any additional medical or nursing care will be delivered free of charge as is done in the routine care of all other patients with Buruli ulcer.

Benefit(s):

There are no direct benefits to you or your child, but the information we collect will be helpful for future Buruli ulcer patients, as we learn more about how your body adjust to the presence of Buruli ulcer germs in your child's body. Standard diagnostic tests done at the KCCR to confirm if the disease is Buruli ulcer or not will be done free of charge. The laboratory tests done free of charge will also help your child's doctor to manage you better.

Dissemination

Once the study results become available, they will be explained to the participants in lay terms and also to the community leaders. In addition, the results will be presented to the hospital staff at the study site. The results will be presented to the National Buruli Ulcer Control Programme at the National Steering committee meeting and to the local communities. Results will be provided to the Ethics Committee; the Regulatory bodies on request. Results may be published in open access peer reviewed journals and progress of study presented at the annual WHO meeting on Buruli ulcer.

Confidentiality:

We will keep confidential any information related to this study and all data and records generated in the course of conducting the study, and will not use the information, data, or records for any purpose other than those specified in this study protocol.

All information collected in this study will be given code numbers. No name will be recorded. Data collected cannot be linked to your child in anyway. No name or identifier will be used in any publication or reports from this study.

All the study information will be kept securely either in the archive at the KCCR or on password protected computer for 10 years after which they will be discarded. Only the investigators will have full access to your data. To ensure your safety and protocol adherence, all data records and other trial related documents will be made available to the Ghana FDA or the trial sponsor (LSHTM) during Good Clinical Practice (GCP) inspections.

Voluntariness:

Taking part in this study should be out of you and your child's own free will. Your child is not under any obligation to participate; it is entirely voluntary. Take your time to think about it and feel free to discuss with family members, elders and others. You will have 48 hours to consider whether you are willing for your child participate or not. Even after agreeing to participate you have the right to withdraw later, without the need to explain why you/your child are withdrawing. If you withdraw we will not keep any further information about your child.

Alternatives to participation:

If you choose not to participate, it will be of no consequence to you or your child, and you will not be approached again. Your child will receive standard medical treatment which consists of at least 8 weeks of antibiotics and gauze dressings.

Withdrawal from the research:

You may choose to withdraw your child from the research at any time without having to explain yourself. You/your child may also choose not to answer any question you find uncomfortable or private. New information that is relevant to your child as a study participant will be made known to you/your child appropriately and you may choose to withdraw from the study or continue with it based on the information given to you.

Consequences of Withdrawal:

Don't feel obliged to participate: this decision is yours and your child's. Even after you decided for your child to participate you may still reconsider and decide to withdraw even if you signed to participate earlier. You are not obliged to explain why you changed your mind: you alone may decide to continue in the study or not. If you withdraw, this will not affect the way you or your child will be treated. Also, even if you want to continue, the doctor may decide that it is in your best interest to withdraw from the study. He or she will explain why this should happen. If you or your child don't feel like participating in the study, there will be no adverse consequence and no loss of benefit or care.

Costs/Compensation:

The study will take up some of your/your child's time. As a compensation for your participation, you will be given small supplies of food worth 30GhC (5.5 euros) and vitamin supplements. Also, any costs related to this study (including transport – about GHs 10), will be reimbursed based on your distance from the clinic. Any other cost you incur in transportation to the clinic due to COVID-19 will be reimbursed. Standard PCR diagnostic tests done at the laboratory to confirm if the disease is Buruli ulcer or not will be paid for by this research study. This provision will also cover those that do not agree to participate. Any ill effect of the treatment requiring additional medical or nursing care will be delivered free of charge.

Contacts:

If you have any question concerning this study, please do not hesitate to contact Dr Yaw Ampem Amoako of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital on 0244858075.

If you have any concern about the conduct of this study, your welfare or your rights as a research participant, you may contact:

The Chairman

Committee on Human Research and Publications Ethics

KNUST - Kumasi

Tel: +233 3220 63248 / +233 20 545 3785

You may also contact the administrator of Ghana health service Ethics Review Committee, Nana Abena Apatu on 050 353 9896 in case you have any concern.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION FOR COVID-19

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a communicable respiratory disease caused by a new strain of coronavirus that causes illness in humans.

Know how it spreads

- There is currently no vaccine to prevent coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).
- **The best way to prevent illness is to avoid being exposed to this virus.**
- The virus is thought to spread mainly from person-to-person.
 - Between people who are in close contact with one another (within about 6 feet).
 - Through respiratory droplets produced when an infected person coughs, sneezes or talks.
 - These droplets can land in the mouths or noses of people who are nearby or possibly be inhaled into the lungs.
 - Some recent studies have suggested that COVID-19 may be spread by people who are not showing symptoms.

Symptoms

People with COVID-19 have had a wide range of symptoms reported – ranging from mild symptoms to severe illness. Symptoms may appear **2-14 days after exposure to the virus**. People with these symptoms **may** have COVID-19:

- Fever or chills
- New loss of taste or smell
- Cough
- Shortness of breath or difficulty breathing
- Fatigue
- Muscle or body aches
- Headache
- Sore throat
- Congestion or runny nose
- Nausea or vomiting
- Diarrhea

Best Health Practices

There is currently no vaccine or treatment for COVID-19

Infection can be prevented by observing personal hygiene practices:

Hand Washing

Wash your hands often

- Wash your hands often with soap and water for at least 20 seconds especially after you have been in a public place, or after blowing your nose, coughing, or sneezing.
- If soap and water are not readily available, **use a hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol**. Cover all surfaces of your hands and rub them together until they feel dry.
- **Avoid touching your eyes, nose, and mouth** with unwashed hands.

Avoid close contact

- **Avoid close contact with people who are sick, even inside your home.** If possible, maintain 6 feet between the person who is sick and other household members.
- **Put distance between yourself and other people outside of your home.**
 - Remember that some people without symptoms may be able to spread virus.
 - Stay at least 6 feet (about 2 arms' length) from other people.
 - Do not gather in groups.
 - Stay out of crowded places and avoid mass gatherings.
 - Keeping distance from others is especially important for people who are at higher risk of getting very sick.

Cover your mouth and nose with a cloth face cover when around others

- You could spread COVID-19 to others even if you do not feel sick.
- Everyone should wear a cloth face cover when they have to go out in public, for example to the grocery store or to pick up other necessities.
 - Cloth face coverings should not be placed on young children under age 2, anyone who has trouble breathing, or is unconscious, incapacitated or otherwise unable to remove the mask without assistance.
- The cloth face cover is meant to protect other people in case you are infected.
- Do NOT use a facemask meant for a healthcare worker.
- Continue to keep about 6 feet between yourself and others. The cloth face cover is not a substitute for social distancing.

Cover coughs and sneezes

- **If you are in a private setting and do not have on your cloth face covering, remember to always cover your mouth and nose** with a tissue when you cough or sneeze or use the inside of your elbow.
- **Throw used tissues** in the trash.
- Immediately **wash your hands** with soap and water for at least 20 seconds. If soap and water are not readily available, clean your hands with a hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol.

Clean and disinfect

- **Clean AND disinfect frequently touched surfaces daily.** This includes tables, doorknobs, light switches, countertops, handles, desks, phones, keyboards, toilets, faucets, and sinks.
- **If surfaces are dirty, clean them.** Use detergent or soap and water prior to disinfection.
- **Then, use a household disinfectant.**

Monitor Your Health

- **Be alert for symptoms.** Watch for fever, cough, shortness of breath, or other symptoms **of COVID-19.**

Health Facility

If you have more severe symptoms go to a medical facility and immediately notify the first person you encounter that you are worried that you have a respiratory infection.

For our Study,

- We will ask that you will always wear a face mask before coming to the clinic. If you do not have one, we will provide you with one which you will wear throughout the procedures.
- Kindly comply with us when we ask that you wash your hands with soap under running water/alcohol-based sanitizers.
- In the examination room, we will ensure that not more than two health workers/ researchers attend to you. if they are more than that, kindly draw their attention to it.
- We will introduce a new sitting arrangement at the waiting are; kindly comply with this anytime you come for review to ensure proper social distancing protocols.

CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF RESEARCH: EVALUATION OF HIGH DOSE RIFAMPICIN AND DIALKYL CARBAMOYL CHLORIDE (DACC)-COATED DRESSINGS TO IMPROVE OUTCOMES IN MYCOBACTERIUM ULCERANS DISEASE

PARTICIPANTS' STATEMENT

Statement	Please initial or thumbprint* each box
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet dated.....(version.....) for the above named study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that consent for my child is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw this consent at any time without giving any reason and without my/the participant's medical care or legal rights being affected.	
I understand that relevant sections of the participant's medical notes and data collected during the study may be looked at by authorised individuals from [insert company/institution names of any one who will have access], where it is relevant to my/the participant's taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to these records.	
I understand that data about the participant may be shared via a public data repository or by sharing directly with other researchers, and that I will not be identifiable from this information	
I understand that the tissue sample collected from the participant will be used to support other research in the future, and may be shared anonymously with other researchers, for their ethically-approved projects	
I give permission for a copy of this consent form, which contains the participant's personal information, to be made available to the Trial Coordinating Centre for monitoring purposes only.	
I agree to the participant taking part in the above named study.	

Name of Participant.....

Participants' SignatureOR Thumb Print.....

Date:.....

INTERPRETERS' STATEMENT

I interpreted the purpose and contents of the Participants' Information Sheet to the afore-named participant to the best of my ability in the (English / Twi) language to his proper understanding.

All questions, appropriate clarifications sort by the participant and answers were also duly interpreted to his/her satisfaction.

Name of Interpreter.....

Signature of Interpreter..... OR Thumb Print

Date:.....

Contact Details

STATEMENT OF WITNESS

I was present when the purpose and contents of the Participant Information Sheet was read and explained satisfactorily to the participant in the language he/she understood (English / Twi)

I confirm that he/she was given the opportunity to ask questions/seek clarifications and same were duly answered to his/her satisfaction before voluntarily agreeing to be part of the research.

Name:.....

Signature.....

Date:.....

INVESTIGATOR STATEMENT AND SIGNATURE

Brief statement or declaration that investigator has given enough information to participants to make informed decisions.

I certify that the participant has been given ample time to read and learn about the study. All questions and clarifications raised by the participant have been addressed.

Researcher's name.....

Signature

Date.....

Participant Information Leaflet- Adult participant

Participant ID.....

Title of Research: Evaluation of High Dose Rifampicin and Dialkylcarbamoyl chloride (DACC)-coated dressings to improve outcomes in *Mycobacterium ulcerans* disease

Name(s) and affiliation(s) of researcher(s) of applicant(s):

This study is being conducted by Prof. R.O. Phillips of Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology and Kumasi Centre for Collaborative Research in Tropical Medicine (KCCR)/ KNUST, Dr. Michael Marks of London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (LSHTM) and other researchers in Ghana and Europe.

Purpose(s) of research: The aim of the study is to determine the ability of high-dose Rifampicin and DACC dressing (HR-DACC) to improve the time to clearance of viable mycobacterium from Buruli ulcer wounds compared to a regimen using standard dose Rifampicin and DACC dressings (SR-DACC).

Background information

The wound or the swelling you have is caused by an organism called *Mycobacterium ulcerans*. There are several approaches for managing this condition. One is the availability of antibiotics (usually standard rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin) that can be used to treat the disease once it is confirmed as Buruli ulcer. These drugs kill the organism that is causing the disease. Rifampicin is the main drug used for treatment. Scientist have found out that a higher dose of the drug is safe and can help improve healing outcome and may shorten the period/ duration for taking the drugs.

Those with wounds also go through wound dressing procedures at the hospitals and the various health centers in the communities. Some materials used include Vaseline gauze and bandages. However, we have observed that some people heal faster than others even with the antibiotic treatment. Some still have living organisms in their wounds many weeks after the antibiotic treatment. There is a new dressing material called DACC which Scientists believe permanently binds bacteria (organisms) on the wound surface leading to their removal when the dressings are changed. This is a good way to prevent infection without the use of more drugs.

We want to test the high dose Rifampicin to see how it can shorten the healing time. We also want to test this new material (DACC) to see if it helps to prevent infection and improve the time of healing in Buruli ulcer wounds.

By doing so we will see if this can help kill the bacteria more quickly and speed up wound healing. We will also collect data to help us see the cost of these different treatments and the impact that Buruli ulcer and its treatment have on you/your family's income or ability to work or study. Both groups will receive the same care and we will monitor everyone. We will use computer to do this so we don't know who will take the high dose Rifampicin or standard dose Rifampicin treatment.

Nature of Research

Procedure of the research, what shall be required of each participant and approximate total number of participants that would be involved in the research:

Role of investigators

Before we let you take part in the study, we will explain to you further and give you time to understand and ask questions. We will let you sign and officially become part of the study. We will do a short physical examination and ask you questions about your Buruli ulcer (swelling or wound) and your current life. We will examine the Buruli ulcer, measure and take photo of the wound. We will give you antibiotics (either standard or high dose rifampicin in combination with Clarithromycin) once we confirm you have Buruli ulcer depending on the group you fall in. All patients will receive the new DACC dressing materials. We will monitor your healing progress and ask you questions anytime we see you to ensure your safety. We will take fine needle aspirates or swabs from the swelling or wound.

Role of participants

You will be given antibiotics either a combination of rifampicin 20mg/kg and clarithromycin 15mg/kg for 4 weeks or rifampicin 10mg/kg and clarithromycin 15mg/kg for 8 weeks and a new treatment dressing (DACC) to put on your sores and they will be changed every other day for 8 weeks.

As part of participants' responsibility to the study, you will be invited to arrive at the center where the study is performed during an already scheduled time for a hospital visit. When you start treatment, you will be required to come for reviews at weeks 2, 4, 6, 8 and monthly until the 12th month when your sore heals completely and we are sure of no recurrence.

However, in this period of COVID-19 pandemic, you may be scheduled for monthly visits only once your lesion heals even during the period of taking antibiotics. You will be given the drugs to cover the period before the next review and you will be monitored by the health volunteer from your community/ village.

Anytime you notice anything unusual once you start taking the antibiotics and the dressing materials, report to the doctors that come to see you. You can also call the numbers provided on this form in case you require any assistance or clarification.

Samples to be taken and their uses

To know if the swelling or wound you have is Buruli ulcer, we will take fluid with needle called fine needle aspirate from the swelling and/ or cotton swab sample from the wound, to know if the organism causing the Buruli ulcer is alive or not and to also find out if there are other organisms present in the wound that can cause secondary infections. We will take these samples at weeks 0,2,4,6,8 and at week 12 and 16 if your wound does not heal.

These samples will be transported and examined in the laboratory at KCCR in Kumasi to determine if the disease is Buruli ulcer. All biological samples obtained from you for this study will be analysed within the lifetime of the project which is 5 years. Permission will be sought from the ethics committee of the Ghana Health Service and Food and Drugs Authority (FDA) should there be any unanticipated delay.

Number of participants

A total of just over 112 participants will be recruited into the study; half will use the high dose rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin 15mg/kg daily and the other half will use the

standard dose rifampicin in combination with clarithromycin 15mg/kg daily. All patients will receive DACC material for their wound dressing.

Risk(s):

There are no substantial risks from the samples that would be taken. Sample collection for the study is in line with standard diagnostic procedures carried out as part of routine patient care. Samples for diagnosis will be collected either via a swab or fine needle aspiration. Fine needle aspirates may cause minor pain. All procedures will be conducted by trained personnel. The new dressing may cause itch from the adhesive; when this occurs, report to the doctor immediately.

Taking this new drug (Rifampicin), you may experience some reactions which may include dizziness, fever, headache, itching, and skin rash but not limited. You are encouraged to talk to your doctor anytime you have an unusual feeling after taking this drug.

We will minimize this risk by getting a qualified person to perform all procedures. Any additional medical or nursing care will be delivered free of charge as is done in the routine care of all other patients with Buruli ulcer.

Benefit(s):

There are no direct benefits to you, but the information we collect will be helpful for future Buruli ulcer patients, as we learn more about how your body adjust to the presence of Buruli ulcer germs in your body. Standard diagnostic tests done at the KCCR to confirm if the disease is Buruli ulcer or not will be done free of charge. The laboratory tests done free of charge will also help your doctor to manage you better.

Dissemination

Once the study results become available, they will be explained to the participants in lay terms and also to the community leaders. In addition, the results will be presented to the hospital staff at the study site. The results will be presented to the National Buruli Ulcer Control Programme at the National Steering committee meeting and to the local communities. Results will be provided to the Ethics Committee; the Regulatory bodies on request. Results may be published in open access peer reviewed journals and progress of study presented at the annual WHO meeting on Buruli ulcer.

Confidentiality:

We will keep confidential any information related to this study and all data and records generated in the course of conducting the study, and will not use the information, data, or records for any purpose other than those specified in this study protocol.

All information collected in this study will be given code numbers. No name will be recorded. Data collected cannot be linked to you in anyway. No name or identifier will be used in any publication or reports from this study.

All the study information will be kept securely either in the archive at the KCCR or on password protected computer for 10 years after which they will be discarded. Only the investigators will have full access to your data. To ensure your safety and protocol adherence, all data records and other trial related documents will be made available to the Ghana FDA or the trial sponsor (LSHTM) during Good Clinical Practice (GCP) inspections.

Voluntariness:

Taking part in this study should be out of your own free will. You are not under any obligation to participate; it is entirely voluntary. Take your time to think about it and feel free to discuss with family members, elders and others. You will have 48 hours to consider whether you are willing to participate or not. Even after agreeing to participate you have the right to withdraw later, without the need to explain why you are withdrawing. If you withdraw we will not keep any further information about you.

Alternatives to participation:

If you choose not to participate, it will be of no consequence to you, and you will not be approached again. You will receive standard medical treatment which consists of at least 8 weeks of antibiotics and gauze dressings.

Withdrawal from the research:

You may choose to withdraw from the research at any time without having to explain yourself. You may also choose not to answer any question you find uncomfortable or private. New information that is relevant to you as a study participant will be made known to you appropriately and you may choose to withdraw from the study or continue with it based on the information given to you.

Consequences of Withdrawal:

Don't feel obliged to participate: this decision is yours. Even after you decided to participate you may still reconsider and decide to withdraw even if you signed to participate earlier. You are not obliged to explain why you changed your mind: you alone may decide to continue in the study or not. If you withdraw, this will not affect the way you will be treated. Also, even if you want to continue, the doctor may decide that it is in your best interest to withdraw from the study. He or she will explain why this should happen. If you don't feel like participating in the study, there will be no adverse consequence and no loss of benefit or care.

Costs/Compensation:

The study will take up some of your time. As a compensation for your participation, you will be given small supplies of food worth 30GhC (5.5 euros) and vitamin supplements. Also, any costs related to this study (including transport – about GHs 10), will be reimbursed based on your distance from the clinic. Any other cost you incur in transportation to the clinic due to COVID-19 will be reimbursed. Standard PCR diagnostic tests done at the laboratory to confirm if the disease is Buruli ulcer or not will be paid for by this research study. This provision will also cover those that do not agree to participate. Any ill effect of the treatment requiring additional medical or nursing care will be delivered free of charge.

Contacts:

If you have any question concerning this study, please do not hesitate to contact Dr Yaw Ampem Amoako of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital on 0244858075.

If you have any concern about the conduct of this study, your welfare or your rights as a research participant, you may contact:

The Chairman

Committee on Human Research and Publications Ethics

KNUST - Kumasi

Tel: +233 3220 63248 / +233 20 545 3785

You may also contact the administrator of Ghana health service Ethics Review Committee, Nana Abena Apatu on 050 353 9896 in case you have any concern.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION FOR COVID-19

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a communicable respiratory disease caused by a new strain of coronavirus that causes illness in humans.

Know how it spreads

- There is currently no vaccine to prevent coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19).
- **The best way to prevent illness is to avoid being exposed to this virus.**
- The virus is thought to spread mainly from person-to-person.
 - Between people who are in close contact with one another (within about 6 feet).
 - Through respiratory droplets produced when an infected person coughs, sneezes or talks.
 - These droplets can land in the mouths or noses of people who are nearby or possibly be inhaled into the lungs.
 - Some recent studies have suggested that COVID-19 may be spread by people who are not showing symptoms.

Symptoms

People with COVID-19 have had a wide range of symptoms reported – ranging from mild symptoms to severe illness.

Symptoms may appear **2-14 days after exposure to the virus**. People with these symptoms **may** have COVID-19:

- Fever or chills
- New loss of taste or smell
- Cough
- Shortness of breath or difficulty breathing
- Fatigue
- Muscle or body aches
- Headache
- Sore throat
- Congestion or runny nose
- Nausea or vomiting
- Diarrhea

Best Health Practices

There is currently no vaccine or treatment for COVID-19

Infection can be prevented by observing personal hygiene practices:

Hand Washing

Wash your hands often

- Wash your hands often with soap and water for at least 20 seconds especially after you have been in a public place, or after blowing your nose, coughing, or sneezing.
- If soap and water are not readily available, **use a hand sanitizer that contains at least 70% alcohol**. Cover all surfaces of your hands and rub them together until they feel dry.
- **Avoid touching your eyes, nose, and mouth** with unwashed hands.

Avoid close contact

- **Avoid close contact with people who are sick, even inside your home.** If possible, maintain 6 feet between the person who is sick and other household members.
- **Put distance between yourself and other people outside of your home.**
 - Remember that some people without symptoms may be able to spread virus.
 - Stay at least 6 feet (about 2 arms' length) from other people.
 - Do not gather in groups.
 - Stay out of crowded places and avoid mass gatherings.
 - Keeping distance from others is especially important for people who are at higher risk of getting very sick.

Cover your mouth and nose with a cloth face cover when around others

- You could spread COVID-19 to others even if you do not feel sick.
- Everyone should wear a cloth face cover when they have to go out in public, for example to the grocery store or to pick up other necessities.
 - Cloth face coverings should not be placed on young children under age 2, anyone who has trouble breathing, or is unconscious, incapacitated or otherwise unable to remove the mask without assistance.
- The cloth face cover is meant to protect other people in case you are infected.
- Do NOT use a facemask meant for a healthcare worker.
- Continue to keep about 6 feet between yourself and others. The cloth face cover is not a substitute for social distancing.

Cover coughs and sneezes

- **If you are in a private setting and do not have on your cloth face covering, remember to always cover your mouth and nose** with a tissue when you cough or sneeze or use the inside of your elbow.
- **Throw used tissues** in the trash.
- Immediately **wash your hands** with soap and water for at least 20 seconds. If soap and water are not readily available, clean your hands with a hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol.

Clean and disinfect

- **Clean AND disinfect frequently touched surfaces daily.** This includes tables, doorknobs, light switches, countertops, handles, desks, phones, keyboards, toilets, faucets, and sinks.
- **If surfaces are dirty, clean them.** Use detergent or soap and water prior to disinfection.
- **Then, use a household disinfectant.**

Monitor Your Health

- **Be alert for symptoms.** Watch for fever, cough, shortness of breath, or other symptoms of **COVID-19**.

Health Facility

If you have more severe symptoms go to a medical facility and immediately notify the first person you encounter that you are worried that you have a respiratory infection.

For our Study,

- We will ask that you will always wear a face mask before coming to the clinic. If you do not have one, we will provide you with one which you will wear throughout the procedures.
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Name of Interpreter.....

Signature of Interpreter..... OR Thumb Print

Date:.....

Contact Details

STATEMENT OF WITNESS

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Signature.....

Date:.....

INVESTIGATOR STATEMENT AND SIGNATURE

Brief statement or declaration that investigator has given enough information to participants to make informed decisions.

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Researcher's name.....

Signature

Date.....